

A Tamil Lexical Analysis Framework Based on Tolkappiyam Linguistic Rules

தொல்காப்பிய மொழியியல் விதிகளை அடிப்படையாகக் கொண்ட தமிழ் சொல்லியல் பகுப்பாய்வுகக் கட்டமைப்பு

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Abstract. In today's generation, frequent spelling mistakes in Tamil necessitate advanced tools for accurate linguistic analysis and correction. This study proposes a Tamil lexical analysis framework grounded in the linguistic principles of Tolkappiyam, focusing on MeiMayakkam, a rule governing consonant-vowel harmony. Tolkappiyar's twelve rules on word formation have been reclassified into nine categories and further refined into nineteen rules based on consonantal sequences. By applying these rules, we evaluate the validity of Tamil word formations, demonstrated with examples like 'பக்கம்' ('pakkam') versus 'பக்ம்ம்' ('pakkmm'). A computational analysis of over 53,617 Tamil proper names was conducted to identify words compliant with MeiMayakkam phonotactics. This framework lays the groundwork for developing Tamil linguistic tools akin to advanced NLP platforms such as Grammarly, AntConc, SpaCy, and TextRazor, offering precise phonological and syntactic validation. This study contributes to improving Tamil language technology through the creation of robust lexical analysis frameworks, enabling intelligent text analysis and correction.

இன்றைய தலைமுறையில், தமிழில் அடிக்கடி ஏற்படும் எழுத்துப் பிழைகள் துல்லியமான மொழியியல் பகுப்பாய்வு மற்றும் திருத்தத்திற்கான மேம்பட்ட கருவிகளின் அவசியத்தை உணர்த்துகின்றன. இந்த ஆய்வு, தொல்காப்பியத்தின் மொழியியல் கோட்பாடுகளை அடிப்படையாகக் கொண்ட தமிழ் சொல்லியல் பகுப்பாய்வுக் கட்டமைப்பை முன்மொழிகிறது, குறிப்பாக மெய்மயக்கம் என்ற மெய்-உயிர்மை இணக்க விதிகளை மையமாகக் கொண்டது. தொல்காப்பியரின் பன்னிரண்டு சொற்புருவாக்க விதிகள் ஒன்பது பிரிவுகளாக மறுவகைப்படுத்தப்பட்டு, மெய்யொலித் தொடர்ச்சிகளின் அடிப்படையில் பத்தொன்பது விதிகளாக மேலும் செம்மைப்படுத்தப்பட்டுள்ளன. இந்த விதிகளைப் பயன்படுத்துவதன் மூலம், 'பக்கம்' ('pakkam') மற்றும் 'பக்ம்ம்' ('pakkmm') போன்ற எடுத்துக்காட்டுகளுடன் தமிழ் சொற்களின் சரியான உருவாக்கத்தை மதிப்பிடுகிறோம். 53,617 க்கும் மேற்பட்ட தமிழ் சொந்தப் பெயர்களின் கணினி பகுப்பாய்வு மெய்மயக்கம் ஒலிப்பியல் விதிகளுக்கு இணங்காத சொற்களை அடையாளம் காண மேற்கொள்ளப்பட்டது. இந்தக் கட்டமைப்பானது Grammarly, AntConc, SpaCy மற்றும் TextRazor போன்ற மேம்பட்ட NLP தளங்களைப் போன்ற தமிழ் மொழியியல் கருவிகளை உருவாக்குவதற்கான அடித்தளத்தை அமைக்கிறது, துல்லியமான ஒலியியல் மற்றும் தொடரியல் சரிபார்ப்பை வழங்குகிறது. வலுவான சொல்லியல் பகுப்பாய்வுக் கட்டமைப்புகளை உருவாக்குவதன் மூலம், அறிவார்ந்த உரை பகுப்பாய்வு மற்றும் திருத்தத்தைச் செயல்படுத்துவதன் மூலம், இந்த ஆய்வு தமிழ் மொழி தொழில்நுட்பத்தை மேம்படுத்துவதற்கு பங்களிக்கிறது.

Keywords: Tolkappiyar, Tolkappiyam, Machined Rules, Grammarly, AntConc, SpaCy, TextRazor, Algorithm, MeiMayakkam

1. Introduction

The structure of the Tamil language has been extensively studied in grammatical works, from Tolkappiyam to modern research. Among these, Tolkappiyam stands out for its detailed analysis of Tamil word formation, offering a

comprehensive framework for understanding the internal structure of words [30]. However, contemporary students, often lacking sufficient knowledge of Tamil morphology, commonly make spelling errors, such as replacing 'கண்டான்' (kaṇḍa:n) with 'கன்டான்' (kaṇṭa:n) or 'கந்தான்' (kaṇṭa:n). Such mistakes are prevalent across online platforms and social media, underscoring the urgent need for tools to assist in correct word formation.

This study presents a framework that evaluates the correctness of Tamil words using the linguistic rules from Tolkappiyam, particularly focusing on MeiMayakkam—a system governing consonant-vowel harmony. A small application was developed based on the Python implementation of MeiMayakkam rules. By adhering to Tolkappiyam's grammatical principles, this research can create tools comparable to advanced language processing technologies, such as Firefox's 'Language Tool,' offering unparalleled precision in word validation and correction, including facilities AI-based grammar checker.

The MeiMayakkam rules play a vital role in determining the semantic validity of words. Tolkappiyam's rigorous rule-based system provides an efficient mechanism for constructing grammatically correct words, which can lead to significant technological advancements. While modern digital tools are constantly emerging, the precision of rule-based systems remains unmatched, making Tolkappiyam's linguistic principles invaluable in this context. By utilizing these established grammatical rules, we can ensure both accuracy and consistency in the development of Tamil language technologies, minimizing spelling errors.

Tolkappiyam, recognized as the first grammar text in the Tamil language, dates back to the 14th century BC [11]. Scholars such as N. Deivasundaram have emphasized that Tolkappiyam's linguistic structure forms the basis for modern Tamil computational linguistics [1]. According to K. Balasubramanian, Tolkappiyam provides a detailed breakdown of Tamil's phonetics (ḍeṭṭṭaḍḍiḍḍa:rām), morphology (sollaḍḍiḍḍa:rām), and semantics (poruḍḍiḍḍa:rām) [4][5]. The categorization of linguistic elements into groups (ṭṭṭṭṭṭ), types (vṭṭṭṭṭṭ), and expansions (vṭṭṭṭṭṭ) as outlined by Tolkappiyam, provides a strong foundation for rule creation, allowing for effective computational implementation.

While traditional grammar works like Tolkappiyam and Nannul are human-readable, modern linguists such as N. Deivasundaram highlight the challenge of converting these rules into formats understandable by computers [2]. This research bridges that gap by converting Tolkappiyam's MeiMayakkam rules into computer algorithms. A Python-based system was developed to implement these rules, offering a practical solution for word validation. By building upon this foundational system, the present study proposes refinements for greater accuracy and introduces a rule-based approach to analyze and suggest the appropriate use of Tamil words in technical contexts.

This research distinguishes itself by offering a detailed analysis of Tamil word structures, grounded in Tolkappiyam's MeiMayakkam rules. It paves the way for future technological advancements in Tamil language processing, offering a robust framework for linguistic validation and tool development.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the connection between lexical analysis and Tolkappiyam. Section 3 describes the literature review. Section 4 illustrates the Proposed work. Section 5 describes the experimental details and Section 6 gives the conclusion and future research possibilities.

2. Connect Between Lexical Analysis and Tolkappiyam

The structure of Tamil words is based on the combination of one or more morphemes. For example, the word 'pa:ḍḍiḍḍa:n' ('பாடுகிறான்') is formed by combining the morphemes 'pa:ḍḍ' ('பாடு'), 'kiṭṭu' ('கிறு'), and 'a:n' ('ஆன்'). Understanding how these morphemes are constructed and how they interact is crucial to grasping the process of word formation. In this process, phonemes occur either independently or sequentially to convey meaning. However, the sequential arrangement of phonemes is subject to certain rules. Not all phonemes can combine freely—this limitation is known as morpheme structure constraints. Tamil also follows these constraints, which help prevent spelling mistakes in both spoken and written forms of the language.

Furthermore, whether in morphemes or full words, Tamil does not allow two vowels to appear consecutively at the beginning, middle, or end. When such a combination arises, a consonant is inserted between them, a process known as 'udampadumei' (medial consonant) [31]. This principle forms a fundamental aspect of Tamil word structure.

In addition to vowel constraints, there are specific restrictions on consonants in Tamil. While languages like English and Sanskrit allow for two or three consonants to occur at the beginning of a word, Tolkappiyam introduces the concept of 'MeiMayakkam,' referring to the combination or fusion of consonants. According to these rules, Tamil words cannot begin or end with two or three consonants, though such combinations are permissible in the middle of a word [31].

This discussion highlights the connection between Tamil lexical analysis and Tolkappiyam, demonstrating how Tolkappiyam's phonological rules, such as morpheme structure constraints and MeiMayakkam, are essential for accurate word formation.

3. Literature Review

Before conducting this study, several relevant research works were reviewed. These include *Automatic Identification of MeiMayakkam in Tamil Words Using Rule-Based and Transfer Learning Approaches* [7][16], *Development of the MeiMayakkam Second Rule Based on Tolkappiyam and Nannul Grammar Concepts* [8], *Data Science-Based Corpus Creation for Tolkappiyam* [9], and *App Development to Address the First MeiMayakkam Rule* [10][14][15]. While these studies share a common focus on the MeiMayakkam rules, the current research introduces a distinct solution to the challenges these prior works encountered.

Similar to these studies, A Comprehensive Study of Word Formation in Tamil [19][20], Noun Identification for Tamil Language using Morphophonemic Rules [21], Isolating Word Level Rules In Tamil Language For Efficient Development Of Language Tools [22], Lexical Formatives And Word Formation Rules In Tamil [23], Morphology and Syntax of the Tamil Language [24], Modern Tamil Word Formation Rules in NLP [25], Morphological Analyzer for Classical Tamil Texts: A Rule-based approach [26], Morphological Analyzer for Classical Tamil Texts: A Rulebased approach [27], A Procedural Study On Morphological Analyzers For Tamil Language Using The Lexical -Surface Rule Based Correspondences [28] also explain Tamil word formation. However, they are based on technology .

The reviewed studies emphasize the automatic identification of MeiMayakkam using a combination of rule-based and transfer learning techniques, the development of the second rule from Tolkappiyam and Nannul, corpus creation for Tolkappiyam using data science, and solving issues related to the first MeiMayakkam rule through app development. Although all focus on the application of MeiMayakkam rules, this research distinguishes itself by addressing gaps left in these prior studies and providing a novel approach to Tamil word structure analysis.

Further, this study initiates a foundational exploration of Tamil word structure from a phonological perspective, specifically following Tolkappiyam's MeiMayakkam framework. Nineteen types of consonant cluster rules have been developed for this purpose, representing an extension beyond earlier works, which mainly described the structure of individual words. This research aims to uncover general underlying principles, allowing for the efficient analysis of millions of Tamil words rather than addressing them one by one. As a result, it provides a unique and broader perspective on Tamil word formation.

In the initial phase of this study, an analysis was conducted based on the nine original Tolkappiyam MeiMayakkam rules (Vinoth @EL). Table 1 illustrates examples of words processed by the MeiMayakkam algorithm based on the Tolkappiyam rules:

Rule No.	Tolkaappiyar Rules	Linguistic script	Input Word Sample	Linguistic script
1.	டர்ல்ள்+கசப	ʈ, r, l, [+kə, sə, pə	கேட்க, கற்க, செல்க, கொள்க	ke:ʈkə, kərkə, səlgə, kolgə
2.	ல்ள்+யவ	l, [+jə, və	கொல்யானை, வெள்வளை	koljə:nəj, vɛlvəɔj

Rule No.	Tolkaappiyar Rules	Linguistic script	Input Word Sample	Linguistic script
3.	ங்ஞண்நம்ன்+இ னவொலி(கசடத பற)	ṅ , ṅ , ṅ , n , m , n+kə , sə , t̪ , t̪ , pə , rə	மாங்காய், பிஞ்சு, மண்டை, வந்து, வம்பு, சென்ற	ma:ŋga:j , piɳɟu , maɳɟəj , vəɳɟu , vəmbu , seɳɟə
4.	ண்ன்+கசருபமய வ	ṅ , n+kə , sə , ṅə , pə , mə , jə , və	வெண்களம், வெண்சட்டை	vəɳɟəɳm , vɛɳɟəɳt̪t̪
5.	ஞ்நம்வ்+ய	ṅ , n , m , v+jə	உரிஞ்யாது, தெவ்யாது	uɾiɳɟa:ɟu , t̪evja:ɟu
6.	ம்+வ	m+və	நிலம்வலிது	niɳmvaliɟu
7.	யர்ழ்+க ச த ப ரு ந ம ய வ ங	j , r , t̪+kə , sə , t̪ , pə , ṅə , nə , mə , jə , və	பாய்ச்சு, வாய்த்தது, வேய்ங்குழல், நாய்க்கடி	pa:jɟɟɟu , va:jɟɟu , ve:jɳɟuɳ , na:jkkəɟi
8.	ர்ழ் தவிர -> க்...ன் + க...ன	r , t̪ t̪vira -> k . . . n + kə . . . nə	வாக்கு, அட்டை, அண்ணன்	va:kku , aɳt̪t̪ , aɳɳɳn
9.	ர்ழ் குற்றொற்றாகா	r , t̪ kutt̪oɳt̪a:ga:	வேர், நேர், வார், ஆர்	ve:r , ne:r , va:r , a:r

However, discrepancies were identified during this analysis. To resolve these issues, the rules were revised and expanded, focusing on the phonological characteristics of the Tamil language. This led to the development of a new set of 19 rules, which form the core of this research's next stage of development. Table-2 presents the categorized rules that were used in this study.

4. Proposed Work: Development and Enhancement of MeiMayakkam Algorithms

This research represents the next stage in understanding and refining the structural rules of Tamil word formation, particularly in the context of *MeiMayakkam* (the fusion of consonants) as outlined in the ancient Tamil grammar texts *Tolkappiyam* and *Nannul* [8]. Previous studies have explored *MeiMayakkam* rules using rule-based and transfer learning approaches [7]. However, while these methods identified the required *MeiMayakkam* changes, they were not fully capable of determining the correct standard forms of words, especially when dealing with phonological intricacies. Thus, there was a need for a more refined approach to these grammatical rules.

4.1. Challenges with Existing Algorithms

The previous algorithm attempted to recognize words such as கற்க (kərkə), செல்க (seɳgə), and கொள்க (koɳgə) as valid forms, even though the correct, standard forms of these words are காற்க (ka:rkə), சேல்க (se:ɳgə), and கோள்க (ko:ɳgə). This discrepancy arose from the limitations of the rule application in the algorithm, which was technically sound but not precise enough to filter non-standard words. This gap necessitated a deeper analysis of Tamil word structures based on the core *MeiMayakkam* rules.

4.2. Refinement of MeiMayakkam Rules

To overcome these challenges, the *Tolkappiyam* rules were restructured and reanalyzed. The *MeiMayakkam* rules were rewritten in the order of the Kakara series (a set of specific consonant combinations in Tamil), allowing a clearer understanding of the word structure and more accurate classification of word forms. By analyzing the rules within this

framework, the research moved towards generating a definitive word list for comparison, aiming for more consistent identification of *MeiMayakkam*-related changes.

4.3. The New *MeiMayakkam* Algorithm

Building on this foundation, a new *MeiMayakkam* algorithm was developed to more precisely align with both the classical *Tolkappiyam* grammar and modern Tamil usage. The following Table 2 presents the categorized rules used in this study, with examples of words that exhibit *MeiMayakkam* features.

Table 2: Tolkappiyar Rule-based *MeiMayakkam* Algorithm

Rule No.	Tolkaappiyar Rules	Linguistic Script	Input Word Sample	Linguistic Script
1.	க்+க	k+kə	பக்கம்	pəkkəm
2.	ங்+க, ங	ŋ+kə, ŋə	எங்கும், இங்ஙனம்	ɛŋŋum, iŋŋənəm
3.	ச்+ச	s+tʃə	பச்சை	pətʃtʃəj
4.	ஞ்+ச, ஞ, ய	ɲ+tʃə, ɲə, jə	மஞ்சள். மஞ்ஞை, உரிஞ்யாது	məɲdʒəl, məɲɲəj, uɾiɲjɑ:ɖu
5.	ட்+க, ச, ட, ப	t+kə, sə, tə, pə	கேட்க, கட்செவி, தட்டை, தட்பவெட்பம்	ke:tka, kəttʃe:vi, təttəj, tətʃəve:tpəm
6.	ண்+க, ச, ஞ, ட, ண, ப, ம, ய, வ	ɲ+kə, sə, ɲə, tə, ɲə, pə, mə, jə, və	வெண்களம், வெண்சட்டை, வெண்குருகு, வெண்சாந்து, வெண்ணூண், கெண்டைமீன், வண்ணநாரை, பண்பு, பெண்மயில், பொன்யாது. மண்வலிது	veŋŋəlam, veŋtʃətʃəj, veŋŋəɾu:ku, veŋtʃɑ:ɲɖu, keɲdɛ:mi:n, vəɲɲəna:ɾəj, məɲvəli:ɖu
7.	த்+த	tʃ+tʃ	நத்தை	nəttəj
8.	ந்+த, ந, ய	n+tʃ, nə, jə	பந்து, வெந்நோய், பொருந்யாது	pəɲɖu, venno:j, poruɲjɑ:ɖu
9.	ப்+ப	p+pə	தொப்பை	tʃoppəj
10.	ம்+ப, ம, ய, வ	m+pə, mə, jə, və	அம்பு, அம்மா, திரும்பாது, நிலம்வலிது	əmbu, əmma: tʃiɾuɱpɑ:ɖu, niɻəm:vali:ɖu
11.	ய்+க, ங, ச, ஞ, த, ந, ப, ம, ய, வ	j+kə, ŋə, sə, ɲə, tʃ, nə, pə, mə, jə, və	வேய்கடிது, வேய்ஙனம், வேய்சிறிது, வேய்ஞான்றது, வேய்தீது, வேய்நீண்டது, வேய்பெரிது, வேய்மாண்டது, செய்யாறு, வேய்வலிது	ve:jgədi:ɖu, ve:jɱɱɱɱɱɱɱ, ve:jɱɱɱɱɱɱɱ, se:jjɑ:ɾu, ve:jvəli:ɖu

Rule No.	Tolkaappiyar Rules	Linguistic Script	Input Word Sample	Linguistic Script
12.	ர்+க, ங, ச, ஞ, த, ந, ப, ம, ய, வ	r+ka , றா , சா , நா , டா , னா , பா , மா , ஜா , வா	வேர்கடிது, வேர்ஙனம், வேர்சிறிது வேர்ஞான்றது, வேர்த்து, வேர்நீண்டது, வேர்பெரிது, வேர்மாண்டது, வேர்யாது, வேர்வலிது	ve:rgəɖiɖu , ve:ɾʃiriɖu , ve:ni:ɳɖəɖu , ve:ɾvəliɖu
13.	வீழ்+க, ங, ச, ஞ, த, ந, ப, ம, ய, வ	v+ka , றா , சா , நா , டா , னா , பா , மா , ஜா , வா	வீழ்கடிது, வீழ்ஙனம் வீழ்சிறிது, வீழ்ஞான்றது, வீழ்த்து வீழ்நீண்டது, வீழ்பெரிது, வீழ்மாண்டது, வீழ்யாணை, வாழ்வோர்	vi:ɳɖəɖiɖu , vi:ɳʃiriɖu , vi:ni:ɳɖəɖu , va:və:ɾ
14.	வ்+வ	v+və	செவ்வானம்	se:və:nəm
15.	ல்+க, ச, ப, ல, ய, வ	l+ka , சா , பா , லா , ஜா , வா	செல்க, வல்சி, செல்ப, இல்லை, கொல்யாணை, கொல்வளை	se:lga , vəlɕi , ʃillaɳ , ko:ləvəɳ
16.	ள்+க, ச, ப, ள, ய, வ	l+ka , சா , பா , லா , ஜா , வா	கொள்க, நீள்சினை, கொள்ப, வெள்ளை, வெள்யாறு, கள்வன்	ko:lga , ni:ɳʃinəɳ , ve:lɳəɳ , ka:lva:n
17.	ற்+க, ச, ப, ற	r+ka , சா , பா , ரா	கற்க, முயற்சி, கற்ப, கற்றாழை	kərka , mujəɾʃi , ka:ɳʃa:ɳ
18.	ன்+க, ச, ஞ, ப, ம, ய, வ, ற, ன	n+ka , சா , நா , பா , மா , ஜா , வா , ரா , நா	புன்கண், புன்செய், மென்ஞாண், அன்பு, வன்மை, இன்யாழ், புன்வரகு, மன்றம், மன்னன்	ponɡəɳ , menɳa:ɳ , ənbu , va:nməɳ
19.	ர், ழ் குறில் எழுத்திற்குப் பின்பு வராது	r , ɳ A punctuation mark does not come after a letter	வேர், நேர், வார், ஆர்	ve:r , ne:r , va:r

Table 2 outlines the application of the newly developed MeiMayakkam algorithm, allowing for a systematic and efficient analysis of Tamil words based on Tolkaappiyam's rules. These examples are drawn from both classical literary works by scholars such as Ilamburanar [32] and Natchinarkkiniyar [33], as well as from everyday colloquial usage. This dual perspective ensures that the study remains relevant in both traditional and modern contexts.

4.4. New Algorithm Flow

The following steps outline the flow of the new *MeiMayakkam* algorithm:

1. Initial Setup: Install and configure the required dictionaries for word analysis, laying the foundation for subsequent steps.
2. Variable Initialization: Create variables to track the words under analysis and the statistical data related to correct and incorrect word forms.
3. Rule Invocation: Modify the program to call specific *MeiMayakkam* rules from the core codebase, determining which rule applies to each word.

4. Word Classification: Classify words into categories such as correct, incorrect, and words that do not require analysis. Analyze them and generate statistical summaries.
5. Corpus Analysis: Analyze the words within the research corpus and verify their accuracy. Store correct and incorrect word forms, as well as those excluded from analysis, for future reference.
6. Display Results: Output the final analysis, including the total number of words processed, and provide breakdowns of correct, incorrect, and excluded words.

Example

Consider the word கற்க (karkā). The algorithm identifies it based on the ற் + க, ச, ப, ற (r + kə , sə , pə , rə) rule, recognizing the consonant combination and confirming that it adheres to the proper *MeiMayakkam* structure. Similarly, words such as முயற்சி (mojərtʃi), and கற்றாழை (kətt̪ɑ:ɻəj) are processed, but flagged as incorrect forms because they do not match the standard expected forms மயற்சி (məjərtʃi) and சிற்றாழை (siɻt̪ɑ:ɻəj).

This refined algorithm allows for more accurate identification of correct word forms and enhances our understanding of *MeiMayakkam* changes in Tamil words, and also helps for future research process in deep analysis for Tamil word formation. It represents a significant advancement over previous methodologies and offers a robust tool for Tamil lexical analysis.

Figure - 1, MeiMayakkam Algorithm Flow Chart

5. Results and Analysis

For this study, words were gathered from various commentaries on *Tolkappiyam*, specifically *Ilampuranar urai* (11th century CE), *Naccinarkkiniyar urai* (14th century CE), and *Tamizhannal urai* (2007). These words were categorized into two files: one containing correct words, and another containing words for further analysis. For each correct word in the analysis file, a corresponding erroneous form was also generated. These files served as benchmarks to evaluate the accuracy of the *Tolkappiyam MeiMayakkam* Python program, providing a structured means of testing its efficacy.

This study introduces a new computational tool for archeology research, and the significance of these findings becomes clear when comparing the results obtained from this tool with the statistical data from **preview** research in Table 4.

Table 3 - Rule - Based MeiMayakkam Algorithm Result, Preview data [8] and current research data

S. No.	Output detail	Preview		Count of the word	
		Count of the word	Percentage	Count of the word	Percentage
1.	Total Collection words	2882	100	53617	100
2.	One or Two-Letter Words	12	0.416	2636	4.91
3.	Correct Words in MeiMayakkam Rules	1431	49.7	30399	56.69
4.	Wrong Words in MeiMayakkam Rules	717	24.9	430	0.80
5.	Omitted Words in MeiMayakkam Rules	722	25.1	20152	37.58

Figure 2 visualizes the statistical data by comparing the present and preview study, highlighting the improvements achieved through this experimental setup.

Figure - 2, MeiMayakkam Statistics Chart

While traditional spell checkers like **Vaani**, proposed by Neechalkaran, are effective in suggesting correct word forms based on lexical similarity and dictionary matching, they often fall short when the user's error stems from a lack of understanding of **usage-specific variations** in Tamil grammar. In such cases, even if the spelling is corrected, the revised form may still remain **semantically or grammatically invalid**. This is particularly evident in classical Tamil, where **Mei-Mayakkam**—a phonological confusion between hard and soft consonants—can cause subtle yet meaningful errors that ordinary spell checkers may not detect.

By incorporating **Mei-Mayakkam detection**, grounded in **Tolkappiyam's phonological rules**, into existing spell checking frameworks, we can significantly enhance their capability to catch and correct errors arising from

misarticulation or misunderstanding of phoneme-level usage. This deeper linguistic integration not only improves the precision of the correction but also **assists users who may be unaware of the contextual or grammatical implications** of their errors. Thus, the proposed model complements conventional spell checkers by bridging the gap between surface-level spelling correction and **rule-based phonological validation**, offering a more holistic solution for Tamil language processing.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

This research has successfully introduced a novel approach and developed an innovative algorithm that functions as a Python dictionary specifically tailored for *MeiMayakkam* research. By leveraging insights from *Tolkappiyam* and contemporary linguistic principles, the study offers a valuable tool for scholars and researchers delving into the intricacies of Tamil word structure. The algorithm's capacity to identify and analyze *MeiMayakkam* variations that may not be explicitly documented in traditional grammar texts presents a significant advancement in the field of Tamil linguistics. The findings underscore the importance of integrating technology with linguistic research, paving the way for more comprehensive analyses of literary data. This not only enriches our understanding of *MeiMayakkam* but also enhances the overall study of Tamil language morphology.

Looking ahead, several avenues for future research can be pursued. One potential direction involves expanding the algorithm to incorporate additional linguistic rules and exceptions, thereby increasing its accuracy and versatility in handling a wider array of Tamil words. This could involve collaborations with linguistic experts to refine the existing rules and include more comprehensive datasets. Furthermore, integrating machine learning techniques could enhance the algorithm's predictive capabilities, allowing it to learn from new inputs and improve its performance over time. Future studies could also focus on applying the algorithm to various genres of Tamil literature, examining how *MeiMayakkam* manifests across different contexts and styles. Additionally, developing a user-friendly interface for the Python dictionary would make it accessible to a broader audience, including educators and students. This would facilitate the integration of the tool into academic curricula and promote a deeper understanding of *MeiMayakkam* within the Tamil language community. In summary, this research lays a robust foundation for future explorations in *MeiMayakkam* studies, fostering a deeper appreciation for the richness and complexity of Tamil linguistics.

In addition to its utility in enhancing spell-checkers, the proposed Mei-Mayakkam detection framework has broader applications across several core areas of Tamil Natural Language Processing. For example, it can significantly improve the accuracy of **machine translation systems** by disambiguating phonetically similar words that differ in meaning due to consonant confusion. It can also be leveraged in **speech recognition and synthesis systems** to distinguish between subtle phonemic variations, particularly in dialectal Tamil, improving both transcription quality and user interaction. To facilitate wide adoption, the framework is designed to be **modular and API-ready**, allowing it to be seamlessly integrated with existing spell-checking tools such as Vaani. A user-friendly interface is planned for future versions, which would allow non-technical users, including students, educators, and writers, to benefit from real-time phonological feedback as they type. This integration will offer a more linguistically grounded and context-aware language assistance system for Tamil.

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